

As-Encountered Prediction of Tunnel Boring Machine Performance Parameters Using Recurrent Neural Networks

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ABSTRACT

Earth Pressure Balance (EPB) Tunnel boring machines (TBMs) are advanced excavation machinery used to efficiently drill through subsurface ground layers while placing precast concrete tunnel segments. They have become prevalent in tunneling projects due to their adaptability, speed, and safety. Optimal usage of these machines requires information and data about the soil of the worksite that the TBM is drilling through. In this paper, we propose the utilization of Artificial Intelligence and machine learning, particularly Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), to predict the operational parameters of the TBM. In the proposed model, we utilize only performance data from excavation segments prior to the location of the machine as well as its current operating parameters to predict the as-encountered parameters. We evaluated the proposed method on a dataset collected during a tunneling project in North America. The results demonstrate that the model is effective in predicting operation parameters. To address the potential issue of gathering sufficient data to retrain the model, we test the possibility of transferring the trained model from one tunnel to another. The results suggest that the model is capable of performing accurately with minimal or even no re-training.

Keywords: Earth Pressure Balance (EPB), Tunnel Boring Machines (TBM), Tunneling, Machine Learning, Recurrent Neural Networks

INTRODUCTION

Shield-driven tunneling using Tunnel Boring Machines (TBM) has become a popular underground construction technique in various geological conditions with minimal surface disruptions. The advantage of using such technology is that while excavating, the TBM is placing a tunnel liner of sequential rings composed of precast segments (Figure 1). The advancement of the machine is powered by thrust cylinders while an erector places the interlocking segments. Thrust load depends on the type of soil and other factors such as groundwater pressure. However, the typical cutterhead thrust load for excavating in soft soil conditions is 10 to 20 percent of the total TBM thrust (1). Another important component of the TBM is the cutterhead, which is located at the frontal contact area of the machine during the excavation process. Selection of the optimal configuration of the cutterhead, such as the cutter type, spacing of the cutters, cutterhead shape and balance of the head, depends (2) mainly on the expected ground conditions. Cutter rotation speed and the tangential velocity of the cutterhead (herein referred to as cutterhead speed) are two of the notable TBM performance parameters that are collected continuously during the excavation. The later parameters, as well as the other machine operational information such as advancement speed, thrust force, and articulation force, are recorded and stored for each tunneling project. We do not consider the control of surface settlements caused by the operation of the machine in this study. Only a portion of the available data is utilized by the TBM operators, mostly during the excavation to advance the machine along the designated alignment. Real-time sequential estimation of such information can significantly improve the operational performance and avoid any unpredicted encounters. These improvements would provide significant benefit to those in the underground transportation engineering community. The following section includes a brief review of relevant studies in the literature.

Figure 1 – a) Structure and Components of a Tunnel Boring Machine (www.railsystem.net), b) Hierarchical structure of the tunnel rings composed of precast segments (3)

BACKGROUND

A number of studies in the literature were focused on predicting the operational parameters of TBM as well as information relevant to the geological environment along the tunneling alignment (4). Some of these efforts were limited to specific ground conditions and environmental factors, while some others showed limited ability to estimate the as-encountered TBM operational parameters. TBM performance prediction models are generally classified into three groups: theoretical models based on laboratory tests, empirical models based on field performance of TBM, and data-driven models based on as-encountered operation parameters during excavation (5). Although there are several studies in the literature focused on developing and updating the first

two types of models, only a few studies were dedicated to developing data-driven algorithms with minimal dependency on empirical parameters.

Mooney et al. (6) and Mokhtari et al. (7) using support vector regression and polynomial regression, respectively, to predict the advance speed during EPB TBM tunneling. They used key EPB TBM parameters to train fairly accurate models and showed that the model relationships varied significantly across different soil types, e.g. sand, silt, clay. The models indicated ranges of soil-specific operational parameters such as net thrust, cutterhead torque, foam flow rate, etc., where advance rate could be increased. Toth et al. (8) analyzed TBM performance in various conditions to understand the impact of ground composition on TBM performance. They focused on addressing the inability of models to predict the TBM penetration rate in mixed ground conditions by analyzing performance in homogeneous conditions. Prediction of penetration rate has been popular in recent TBM predictive analysis techniques, as the feature is an important part of understanding excavation performance. However, due to the limitations of their predictive model to a specific geological composition, a lot more data is needed to generalize the model to be applicable to a variety of underground conditions. They found direct correlations between penetration rate and geological parameters but claim that additional research will be required to find out if their results are comprehensive enough, given the presence of outside factors such as logistics or operator experience.

Avunduk et al. (9) developed a process to predict the excavation performance based only on soil properties. They showed accuracy in predicting cutterhead performance and thrust force based on single-variate and multi-variate analysis of soil composition with a simple regression model. Bilgin et al. (10) analyzed TBM performance based on rock composition in fractured rock formations. They developed a model using a stochastic estimator and a Monte Carlo simulation for predicting performance in clayey soil. However, they found that the applicability of the model in other geological conditions is limited. The results of this model in coarse material are subject to inaccuracies, due to the presence of other additives, as well. The resultant model, although accurate in predicting the penetration rate, fails to estimate cutterhead torque and thrust with similar accuracy. These features are important to understand TBM performance as they reflect the machine's ability to excavate.

Farrokh et al. (11) reviewed the accuracy of models in predicting hard rock TBM performance with neural networks using primary mechanical data. They found that the model does not propose reasonable predictions compared to traditional methodologies. They also concluded that most existing predictive models, both traditional and computer-aided, cannot offer accurate estimates of hard rock TBM performance on new excavations without significant re-training. They suggest that this is due to a lack of inclusion of essential parameters and that an accurate record of operational parameters from a variety of test sites could help in improving the reliability of prediction models.

Salimi et al. (12) employed several artificial intelligence techniques to predict the advancement rate and other performance parameters of the TBM using the data extracted from two hard rock tunneling sites. Those techniques include principal component analysis (PCA) as a pre-processing approach and artificial neural networks (ANN), adaptive neuro-fuzzy inference system (ANFIS) and support vector regression (SVR) to develop the prediction models. They evaluated the performance of prediction models using root mean square error (RMSE), variance account for (VAF), and mean absolute percentage error (MAPE). Their study found that although all prediction models showed acceptable performance, the SVR method outperformed the other two models.

However, only one parameter known as field penetration index (FPI) was predicted under limited ground conditions.

The main objective of this study was to evaluate the possibility of implementing a recurrent neural network (RNN), a machine learning technique, to predict some of the operational parameters of TBM, using earlier operating data during the excavation process. We extracted TBM data from a tunneling project in North America that involved the construction of a parallel set of tunnels. Our study also evaluates the possibility of applying training data from one tunnel to another with both minimal and nonexistent re-training. The following sections include the process of data extraction, pre-processing, model development, and validation.

DATASET PROCESSING AND PROCEDURE

Dataset

The dataset used for this project was extracted from two parallel tunnels in North America using an earth pressure balance TBM. Data were separated into two series, for each tunnel, and further subdivided by location of tunnel rings along the excavation alignment. The TBM collected approximately 40,000 rows of data samples per tunnel, during a period of about six months, with a total of about 1100 rings from each tunnel.

Feature Extraction and Elimination

To prevent tautological bias, a correlation heatmap was created to identify features that were directly mapped to one another. Certain features that were being derived directly from other sources were removed to prevent any overlap or bias between features and labels. Some TBM sensors collected data per ring rather than collecting continuous operation data similar to other TBM sensors, which generated an irregularity in the sampling rate. To address this issue, several statically derived features were calculated based on the collected data within each ring to aggregate and compress their information and append it to the ring they were associated with. The statistical features derived from the intra-ring samples were mean, median, range, max, min, kurtosis, skewness, standard deviation, and quartiles. The addition of each of these features per TBM sensor compensated for the loss of high-definition that had been provided by the intra-ring samples while matching the sampling rate to that of the lower-rate sensors. The feature data is then normalized to avoid any scaling concerns. A simple min-max scaling is used as follows:

$$Scale = \frac{x_i - x_{min}}{x_{max} - x_{min}} \quad (1)$$

where x_i is the feature value, x_{max} and x_{min} are the maximum and minimum value for each feature.

The TBM operation data was processed through a Recurrent Neural Network (RNN) to predict performance parameters. The key characteristic of the RNN is its ability to take samples in previous timesteps and utilize that data to predict the samples in the future. In order to do this, the data is reshaped into a three-dimensional matrix, with dimensions: features, samples, and time steps. Figure 2 shows the schematic of the data format.

Figure 2 Input Data format for RNN model

The prediction for time t is made only based on previous timesteps $t-3$, $t-2$, and $t-1$. This approach enables the model to predict features denoted by labels ahead of the machine at the future timestep t . The previous timesteps should be sufficiently in the past to discount TBM inertia. In this study, we utilized three previous timesteps, since passed that threshold, noise will be added to the data. This approach was applied to both datasets. The availability of two datasets for the adjacent tunnels can be used to verify the results of the trained model. By utilizing the same neural network structure on both tunnels, and verifying the same levels of accuracy, we were able to determine if the model could be applicable to a different excavation environment.

Another application is the ability of the network to derive generalized inferences that can be applied to parallel tunnels with minimal, or even zero, training. Such a result would imply that this model can be used to improve and predict TBM performance on parallel tunnels in similar ground. Eliminating the need for prior analysis, or at least reducing it, greatly advances current construction techniques.

In order to evaluate this possibility, no geological data was used in training the model. It was only exposed to mechanical data, so that transferability from one tunnel to the other could be done without accounting for different feature categories or types. Geological differences would be reflected through differences in machine response and performance, and so for the purposes of this experiment, we assumed they were “encoded” in the mechanical features.

To evaluate these scenarios, the model undergoes four experiments. First, it is trained and tested only on a data split of the first tunnel. Second, it is trained and tested on a split of the second tunnel to verify the adaptability of the model structure. Third, it is trained on the first tunnel and tested on the second tunnel without ever having trained on any data from the second tunnel. Finally, the model utilizes all the data from the first tunnel and a minimal amount of data from the second tunnel (<15%) to attempt to achieve results comparable to having been trained only on that tunnel.

PREDICTIVE MODEL

The data is used to train an Artificial Neural Network (ANN). An ANN is generally used to model complex relationships between variables, using a multilayer system with weighted connections. The model is trained on the provided data to adjust both the layers as well as the weights between layers. Standard ANNs are incapable of handling temporal connections. Thus, in this study, we use Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN), a subcategory of ANN, for their ability to model time-based relationships using a memory system. In this case, the temporal connection is between the

past samples and the current one, as they are directly related to one another. Figure 3 shows the structure of an RNN.

Figure 3 Structure of a recurrent neural network (RNN)

Each of the recurrent neurons within the recurrent layer can be structured differently depending on the type of RNN. In this case, a Gated Recurrent Unit (GRU) is used. GRU is a relatively simple recurrent neuron, and one of the more recent developments in this subcategory. It acts as a set of memory cells, each with an input gate and a “forget” gate. The cell remembers information to train the network. The input gate filters the information to be added to the cell while the forget gate chooses information to drop. This allows the cell to derive long-term relations between values while avoiding overly specific short-term relations. This is especially critical in our application (tunneling data), where simple performance relations may be present in a certain subset of geological environment, but not present in the overall pattern. To avoid allowing the predictive system to fall into these sub-relations, rather than finding an overall pattern, the forget system is important to the model.

Another model that was employed was the Long Short-Term Memory Network (LSTM). LSTM adds an additional “output” gate to the GRU cell, to filter the information outflow. However, the additional complexity of the LSTM necessitates a larger amount of training data. The GRU handles the reduced quantity of data better, as it is a simple system with fewer mechanisms to train. Figure 4 visualizes the difference between an LSTM and GRU unit.

Figure 4 A comparison of GRU and LSTM recurrent neurons.

To assess the model’s performance, we split the data into training and validation sets. This separation is defined before the reshaping to prevent any overlap or relationship between the two

sets, ensuring the model is only predicting between features, rather than connecting the training data directly to testing. Separating prior to reshaping prevents any of the past timesteps in the early samples of the validation data overlapping with the late samples in the training set. Therefore, some of the early samples in the validation set must simply be dropped as they do not have enough past samples from their own validation set to be reshaped. To avoid dealing with the lack of testing data, the separation point must be adjusted to favor the validation set more than the standard split.

A search through various optimizers and models showed that the ideal optimizer and error loss for this particular system was the Adam optimizer with an MAE error loss. To handle the relative lack of data, a Gaussian noise filter is introduced during the training stage. The validation set, however, only uses the actual values from the machine. The predictions are then evaluated using the Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this study, we evaluated four scenarios: (1) Training and testing on the first tunnel, (2) training, and testing on the second tunnel, (3) training on the first tunnel and a small (<15%) portion of the second tunnel data and then testing on the remainder of the second tunnel dataset, and finally (4) training only on the first tunnel data and then testing on the second tunnel.

The results of the model performance in predicting critical features of the first tunnel are displayed in Figure 5, compared against the actual machine outputs. The RMSE values for each of the variables are displayed in Table 1, along with the normalized RMSE (RMSE divided by the mean of the parameter). This is necessary since the machine outputs are measured at different scales and need a scale-independent metric.

Figure 5 Comparisons of predictions against actual sensor outputs at future rings. The predictive model is trained and tested on separate datasets from the first tunnel.

Table 1 – Results of the model trained and tested on the first tunnel alone

Predicted Feature	RMSE	NRMSE
Advance Speed (mm/min)	10.8	0.159
Articulation Force (kN)	1200	0.171
Cutterhead Rotation Speed (rpm)	0.472	0.220
Thrust Force (kN)	3390	0.366

Prediction of critical features such as advance speed, thrust force, and articulation force showed noticeable results. Estimation of these features could be used to inform and improve the operation of the TBM. Since each of these predictors is running on the same dataset consisting of the past inputs, with no change being made per label, these predictions can all be run simultaneously to the same degree of accuracy, meaning that the predictor can provide an entire view of all the parameters as they will appear at the next ring. The model shows exceptional abilities in terms of predicting sensor features, particularly considering that it is doing so without the knowledge of the other sensor data at the same ring. The model holds its performance quite consistently throughout several runs.

The same tests were performed on the model being trained and tested only on the second tunnel. Figure 6 and Table 2 provide the results, which are quite similar in scope and accuracy to the results of the first scenario.

Figure 6 Predictions versus actual values. The predictive model is trained and tested on separate datasets from the second tunnel.

Table 2 – Results of training and testing only on the second tunnel

Predicted Feature	RMSE	NRMSE
Advance Speed (mm/min)	9.34	0.166
Articulation Force (kN)	2140	0.283
Cutterhead Rotation Speed (rpm)	0.457	0.212
Thrust Force (kN)	2600	0.248

In the third experiment, the model was trained on the entirety of the first tunnel and approximately 150 rings of the second tunnel, leaving about 900 rings for validation. In order to give a balanced comparison to the model evaluated in the second scenario, this model is not tested on all 900 rings, but only on the last 100 rings, the same ones that second would have evaluated upon. Figure 7 and Table 3 shows the prediction results and accuracy.

Figure 7 Predictions of the model having been trained on the first tunnel plus less than 15% of the second tunnel.

Table 3 – Results of training on the whole of the first tunnel and less than 15% of the second tunnel, predictions on the portion of the second tunnel used in past tests.

Predicted Feature	RMSE	NRMSE
Advance Speed (mm/min)	11.63	0.207
Articulation Force (kN)	1180	0.155
Cutterhead Rotation Speed (rpm)	0.478	0.221
Thrust Force (kN)	2480	0.236

Finally, the model was trained only on the first tunnel data and tested on the second tunnel dataset. In order to give a balanced comparison to the model evaluated in test 2 and 3, this model is tested on the last 100 rings, the same ones that scenario 2 and 3 would have evaluated upon. Figure 8 provides the results of several key features, and Table 4 provides key metrics on these results.

Figure 8 Predictions based on model training only on the first tunnel and testing only on the selected portion of the second tunnel used in Figure 5.

Table 4 – Results of training on the first tunnel and testing on the second.

Predicted Feature	RMSE	NRMSE
Advance Speed (mm/min)	8.10	0.144
Articulation Force (kN)	1360	0.180
Cutter Rotation Speed (rpm)	0.560	0.263
Thrust Force (kN)	2070	0.197

CONCLUSIONS

The results of this paper suggest that utilizing recurrent neural networks would allow for the prediction of critical excavation performance evaluation features in future states. The structure of the model appears to apply to parallel tunnels in the same geological conditions, as verified by the application of the model to two parallel tunnels. Providing light re-training even allowed it to outperform the model fully trained on the tunnel from where the testing data originated. Prediction

of critical features such as advance speed, thrust force, and articulation force showed noticeable results. The model shows successful abilities in terms of predicting sensor features, particularly considering that it is doing so without the knowledge of the other sensor data at the same ring. The model holds its performance quite consistently throughout several runs. The success of the model implies a transferability of training of the RNN predictive model. Such generalization is a feature that will be very useful in optimizing the TBM operation. However, it is important to note that the two tunnels were excavated in parallel, in relatively similar ground conditions. Retraining across two entirely different tunnels in different ground conditions may also be possible but will require further validation with the availability of a larger database. Even with this qualification, the potential improvements resulting from optimization through this method present significant benefit to the underground transportation community.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

The authors confirm contribution to the paper as follows: study conception and design: M. Pourhomayoun, L. Fisher, K. Nagercha, M. Mazari; data collection: K. Nagercha; analysis and interpretation of results: M. Pourhomayoun, L. Fisher, K. Nagercha; draft manuscript preparation: L. Fisher, K. Nagercha, M. Pourhomayoun, M. Mazari, M. Mooney, T. Rodriguez. All authors reviewed the results and approved the final version of the manuscript.

REFERENCES

1. Galván, A., Peña, F., & Moreno-Martínez, J. Y. (2017). Effect of TBM advance in the structural response of segmental tunnel lining. *International Journal of Geomechanics*, 17(9), 04017056.
2. Grothen, B., Optimizing Soft Ground Excavation: Development and Design of EPB and Slurry Cutterheads, Proc. 2015 World Tunnels Congress, Dubrovnik, Croatia, May 22-28, 2015.
3. Yi, C., Lu, D., Xie, Q., Liu, S., Li, H., Wei, M., & Wang, J. (2019). Hierarchical tunnel modeling from 3D raw LiDAR point cloud. *Computer-Aided Design*, 114, 143-154
4. Mooney, M. A., Walter, B., & Frenzel, C. (2012). Real-time tunnel boring machine monitoring: A state of the art review. *North American Tunnelling*, 2012 proceedings, 73-81.
5. Hassanpour, J., Vanani, A. G., Rostami, J., & Cheshomi, A. (2016). Evaluation of common TBM performance prediction models based on field data from the second lot of Zagros water conveyance tunnel (ZWCT2). *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 52, 147-156.
6. Mooney MA, Yu H, Mokhtari S, Zhang X, and Zhou X. EPB TBM Performance Prediction on the University Link U230 Project. *Proc. North American Tunneling Conference*, Washington D.C., June 24-27, 2018.
7. Mokhtari, S., Navidi, W., and Mooney, M.A. White Box Regression (Elastic Net) Modeling of Earth Pressure Balance Shield Machine Advance Rate, *Automation in Construction*, 2020, 115(103208).

8. Toth, A., Gong, Q., and Zhao, J. Case Studies of TBM tunneling performance in rock-soil interface mixed ground. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, Vol. 38, 2013, pp. 140–150.
9. Avunduk, E., and Copur, H. Empirical modeling for predicting excavation performance of EPB TBM based on soil properties. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, Vol. 71, 2018, pp. 340-353.
10. Bilgin, N., Copur, H., Balci, C. Effect of replacing disc cutters with chisel tools on performance of a TBM in difficult ground conditions. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, Vol. 27, 2012, pp. 41-51.
11. Farrokh, E., Rostami, J., Laughton, C. Study of various models for estimation of penetration rate of hard rock TBMs. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, Vol. 30, 2012, pp. 110-123.
12. Salimi, A., Rostami, J., Moormann, C., & Delisio, A. (2016). Application of non-linear regression analysis and artificial intelligence algorithms for performance prediction of hard rock TBMs. *Tunnelling and Underground Space Technology*, 58, 236-246.